

Research careers and research assessment reform: a ‘public values’ perspective

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Abstract

This paper contributes to studies of research careers as a mediating structure that links knowledge production activities and societal institutions and expectations. It develops a ‘public values’ conceptual framework for understanding research careers, building on existing approaches from the sociology of science. It discusses this framework in the context of recent approaches to the reform of research assessment. It argues that a public values approach to research careers is sensitive to the heterogeneity of research careers – in terms of scientific disciplines and career stage – while providing a coherent framework for thinking about these careers in the context of evolving societal expectations about the contributions of publicly funded science.

1. Introduction

Research careers can be understood as a specific social structure that mediates between science and society. As Jochen Gläser (2001: 699) described:

Research careers link individuals and institutions and they link social structures with knowledge production...careers provide a channel for societal influences on knowledge production...one of the phenomena that mediate between the scientific and non-scientific social structures, on the one hand, and knowledge production, on the other hand.

As a mediating structure, research careers should reflect both the professional demands of the scientific community in which it is lived as a working life, and the values and expectations of the broader society in which it is embedded. In the case of public funded science, responsibility exists not just to perform professional tasks to the best standard possible, but to uphold and reflect the values of that society and polity which has designated science as a priority area for investment, in the interests of collective well-being and quality of life (Bozeman and Sarewitz 2011). While the differentiation of society into social fields, such as science, inevitably leads to the institutionalisation of norms of behaviour that are specific to that field, in liberal and social democratic societies an expectation endures that such context specific characteristics remain congruent with those of the society as a whole.

Yet, in the everyday working life of a research scientist how are such anchoring ‘public values’ (Bozeman and Sarewitz 2011) that tie science and society together maintained and enriched? How easy is it for the challenges, trials, and the structure of ubiquitous evaluation that

characterises scientific work life to become all-consuming and self-referential, challenging researchers' perseverance and ethical propriety? Public value research careers (PVRC) is a reflection on how the working life of research scientists can be shaped by institutional conditions and disciplinary practice norms that do not only face inward towards the goal of scientific discovery and knowledge production, but are also open to a broader societal context in which the purpose and value of scientific work is ultimately located.

2. The theoretical problem

The vast majority of studies of research careers investigate the interrelationships between the specific social and intellectual organisation of scientific fields and disciplines (Bourdieu 1975; Gläser & Laudel 2015; Whitley 2000) and the varying institutional conditions and authority relations that characterise the national research systems in which these activities take place (Whitley et al. 2010). The governance of research is dominated by national investments in universities, research performing organisations, infrastructure, and funding support (Whitley et al. 2010).

Only a relatively small discussion has occurred in the scholarly literature regarding the interconnections between *non-scientific* social institutions and structures and knowledge production. For example, connections have been described in terms of science as reproducing social stratification; science as situated in, and to some extent determined by, socio-political contexts; and in focus of this paper, science as a professional field in need of reform or realignment to better service external demand-driven logics, e.g. economic growth, socio-economic transformation for sustainability, etc.

Bourdieu studied the academic field as an example of social reproduction. He highlighted how the academic field was reproduced through its domination by a particular class of French society. The homogeneity of the French scientific profession, as a field occupied by individuals endowed with the range of social and educational capitals that made them a 'natural' fit for the academic world (Bourdieu 1988), is largely replicated around the world. The consequences of this historic domination of the scientific field by a sub-population that does not reflect the broader socio-economic and cultural composition of society is thought to have consequences for knowledge production. For example, the historical focus of health research in developed countries on topics that concern men reflects the persistent underrepresentation of women in science and in positions of leadership in scientific communities (EC 2021). Recent initiatives to improve the 'equity, diversity and inclusion' (EDI) of the scientific workforce and academia reflect an acknowledgement of this phenomenon of the lack of correspondence between the population structure of society and the make-up of the scientific workforce (UKRI 2022; Wellcome Trust 2021).

Another way in which non-scientific social structures are considered in relation to knowledge production is in relation to the importance of broad socio-political factors in the attractiveness of national science systems. Availability of and access to free public health care, including for family members, free public education for children, and labour market access for a spouse or partner are important in decisions to work in a particular national scientific system (Gläser 2004). Religious freedom and relatively low levels of institutional and personal racism and discrimination, and the right to retain dual or multiple citizenships, can also be considered important non-scientific factors that affect immigration decisions. Finally, societies with relatively low levels of corruption and crime, and relatively open and transparent systems of public administration also have an advantage in recruiting researchers (Gläser 2004). In short,

societies that embody a range of positive ‘public values’ (Bozeman and Sarewitz 2011) in their social, economic, and political institutions, are more attractive destinations for migrants, including relatively high-value and high-earning professionals such as scientists.

Recent discussions around the need to re-orient or reform science provide a spotlight under which to study the connections between non-scientific societal institutions and knowledge production. On the one hand, the framing of science and technology as the engine of economic growth and development placed increased demands on public funded researchers and research organisations to (co-)produce knowledge with social utility (Gibbons et al. 1994). The emergence and institutionalisation of whole of society responses to what are variously known as global or societal grand challenges has also had significant effects on the institutional conditions governing science and by extension the epistemic decisions of scientists. Scientists’ research agendas in virtually all fields are being shaped by the increasing emphasis on mission-oriented funding that is designed to ‘direct’ a greater proportion of public funded research toward topics and problems prioritised by socio-political actors and citizens. The institutionalisation of monitoring frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals provide a governance mechanism by which science generally, and research performing organisations in particular, can be assessed in terms of responsiveness and contribution to these societal demands.

On the other hand, there has been a rising level of public concern about the conduct and outcomes of research and innovation. Historically citizens have tended to regard science as a vocation that has integrity and legitimacy and scientists as worthy of public trust. However, the evolution of research culture in ways that are aligned with broader social values and expectations cannot be taken for granted. Scientific research and academia have been beset by a wide range of cultural failures, including research fraud, ethical misconduct, the institutionalisation of questionable research practices (QRPs) in many disciplines (Vitae 2020), along with socially unacceptable behaviour in relation to bullying, the exploitation of junior colleagues, and sexual harassment (UKRI 2020). The emergence of values-based initiatives within science governance, such as responsible research and innovation (RRI) (Owen et al 2012) and EDI movements, reflect evolution in non-scientific societal institutions that can be expected to shape the scientific field over time.

In summary, PVRC takes up these starting points as the basis for a systematic consideration of how research careers can be fit for the demands of knowledge production and the hierarchical intricacies of scientific communities, but also be sensitised and open to evolution in broader societal demands and public expectations. In this short paper it is not possible to further discuss these bases for a public value approach to research careers. Rather, the remainder will focus on the reform of research assessment and how this can be viewed through a PVRC lens.

3. Reform of systems of rewards and recognition

Recent approaches to research assessment reform, most prominently the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), whilst not directly anchoring reform in the rewarding of contribution to public values, attempt to balance traditional assessment criteria of quality and impact with criteria of diversity, inclusiveness and collaboration. The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (2022) on which CoARA’s activities are based, defines its purpose as to ‘broaden recognition of the diverse practices, activities and careers in research, considering the specific nature of research disciplines and other research endeavours’ (p.4). An

impressive wish-list of activities that could foreseeably be deserving of recognition and reward within science is compiled.

A potential shortcoming in this endeavour is that reforms lack a framework or rationale for anchoring recognition also in non-scientific societal institutions and expectations. The risk then is that reform simply reflects specific ‘internal’ concerns that are most pressing to scientific communities in the short-term, stopping short of a reform that opens research careers to the influence of non-scientific societal institutions in the medium and longer term.

Critics of this line of thinking would argue that one of the current major problems with science is that it is already too open to societal influence, particularly the ‘neo-liberal’ co-opting of research and innovation to the objectives of multinational corporations and ‘platform capitalism’ (Mirowski 2018). This is undoubtedly a legitimate concern, however one of the advantages of taking a public values approach to the governance of science and the scripting of research careers is that different activities can be weighed and assessed in context and translated into recognition and rewards based on contributions to public values. Rather than a relatively universalist approach such as that constructed by Merton (1973), which treats science as ultimately governed by a narrow set of intrinsic values, a public values approach can be anchored in both scientific practice and social institutions and be more versatile and sensitive to heterogeneity in contexts of knowledge production and in research careers.

Linking research practices to public values can help move beyond assessments that focus predominantly on narrow definitions of productivity (publications) and impact (citations) that overly value rewarding the products of research over the processes. A reformed research assessment would not just recognise and reward *what* science was done, but *how* it was done. Such an assessment framework would strengthen incentives for doing science in a way that is aligned with and reinforces public values. Such an assessment framework would provide incentives and rewards for the kinds of example practices included in Table 1.

Table 1. Research career attributes and public values

Attribute	Practices	Value mechanisms	Public values
Open Science practices	FAIR data, open-source tools, shared in scientific community and beyond Rapid data sharing & dissemination Documentation of methods	Efficient knowledge production, enhanced inclusion of stakeholders Accelerated responsiveness to societal challenges Reproducibility of results	Efficiency Transparency
Research Integrity practices	External ethics approval acquired Research data management plan Pre-registration of research approach	Assessment of potential harm Process for protection of personal information Reduction in questionable research practices (QRPs)	Integrity Privacy Fairness
Public Engagement practices	Transdisciplinary research collaborations	Co-creation of research agendas Co-production of knowledge	Legitimacy Relevance Efficacy
EDI practices	Elimination of discrimination or bias in training, hiring and promotion	Diversity and gender balance in the workplace	Equality Fairness
Gender content analysis	Consideration and integration of gender issues in the design of research	Research outcomes that address both women and men	Equality Fairness Legitimacy

4. Rewarding public values in research

There are two main reasons why a public values approach could benefit research assessment reform in the longer term. The first is to reassure researchers and scientific communities that research assessment reform need not be regarded as an attack on research freedom, or as a distraction or burden on scientific discovery processes. Second, such an approach can help make explicit that public values may be in tension or conflict in specific contexts of knowledge production, necessitating a process of evaluation and prioritisation of actions that can be grounded in a coherent rationale.

The first point refers to the fact that researchers tend to react in a defensive or antagonistic way to any policy or other initiatives that they perceive could infringe on academic freedom. Policies that can be seen as demands that scientists ‘do more’ or ‘do things differently’ can be viewed as creating additional burdens that distract from the essential work of scientific discovery. Scientists’ research agendas are built around those disciplinary specific tasks that are ‘epistemically necessary’, all those elements of their work and role set that are associated with moving the frontier of knowledge and their own ‘cognitive career’ (Laudel and Gläser 2015) forward. New demands are likely to elicit an expansion in the division of scientific labour in

order to ‘buffer’ epistemic necessity and preserve researchers’ time and resources to focus on core epistemic tasks.

Indeed, the response to increased demands that can currently be observed in many fields is the construction of ‘roles sets’ (Gläser & Laudel 2015) that protect epistemically necessary tasks, activities and functions from interference or dilution. The emergence of such role sets, stretches the scientific division of labour, creating new positions that have a partial or non-existent dedication to epistemically necessary tasks, but rather are engaged primarily in activities such as project, stakeholder, or research data management. Researchers engaged in these role sets may find themselves excluded from the main currency of academic evaluations, authorship of scientific articles, with negative consequences for the progress of their research career. Indeed, such role sets are not recognised or effectively supported by institutional conditions in science systems. Peer review processes in science will continue to privilege epistemic necessity in evaluating the worth of a scientist’s contributions. Roles that are more directly involved in responding to non-scientific societal structures, such as managing liaisons with patient organisations, will struggle to compete for recognition in such contexts.

A public value perspective re-frames the question of what is worthy of recognition and reward beyond lists of tasks to the relevant public values to which any specific research should contribute and reinforce. To use an example, advances in genetic diagnosis in rare diseases rely on collaboration with patient organisations for bio-samples. The work of discovery reported in a scientific journal may reflect a public value of ‘progress’. However, this work of discovery should not be considered independently of the value of ‘privacy’ embedded in work of patient and patient organisation liaison and collaboration that ensured the safety and integrity of processes of using personal information and bio-samples, which made the epistemically necessary work ethically and scientifically possible. Rather, a public values approach requires that evaluation of such research assesses contributions to a range of public values, to ensure that not just research results but all processes integral to their production are also integral to research assessment.

The second point refers to the idea that a public values approach can help make explicit the tensions that can emerge between public values in different contexts of knowledge production. This can support reflection on research objectives and designs that reach beyond a singular focus on the successful execution of epistemically necessary tasks. An example can be described using the adoption of Open Science (OS) research practices. Resistance to adopting OS practices can come from scientists that argue that if OS is epistemically necessary, then a scientific discipline or specialization will already be doing it (Leonelli 2023). Researchers may understand any expectations that they view as not epistemically necessary as undermining or interfering with their capacity to further their cognitive contributions to knowledge in their field, making their research agenda needlessly uncompetitive (‘it will be done anyway’). In such circumstances a researcher may change their research agenda, change their organisational context to a more *laissez-faire* environment, or they may expand the division of labour to buffer their time focusing on epistemically necessary tasks by hiring someone to deal with what are perceived as additional OS tasks (data management plans and procedures, metadata preparation, ontologies, etc.). It is this expansion of the division of labour that leads to the emergence of positions and role sets in research that are not supported by traditional academic evaluation systems.

Workflows, role sets, and the division of labour can configure and institutionalise OS in different ways in specific contexts of knowledge production (Armeni et al. 2021). For example,

while it may not be pragmatic for a late career research Professor to switch their own research practices to Open Science, supporting financially and intellectually the taking up of appropriate OS practices by ECRs in their labs or institutes would be just as important a contribution from a public values perspective. There may be reasons that are separate from epistemic necessity that motivate researchers to adopt OS in some ways: to satisfy funders; to satisfy organisational policy ‘pressure’; to unify and simplify training processes; or to improve accountability for resource use, for example.

There may also be reasons integral to epistemic necessity that limit OS in disciplinary knowledge production practices (Leonelli 2023). For example, in much qualitative social sciences work ensuring the anonymity of participants in data collection methods such as interviews is paramount. Here the public value ‘privacy’ should be prioritised over ‘transparency’. In some biochemistry or virology research fields the public value ‘safety’ should be the highest priority. Anchoring research assessment in public values can thus provide a framework for recognising and rewarding researchers also for the reflexivity and judgement they exercise in balancing tensions between public values, between privacy and transparency for example, or for decisions they make to shift their research agendas due to ethical or safety issues that concern the greater public good.

5. Conclusion

The rationale for PVRC is that the research career, as a social structure that mediates between science and society, could be made more open and responsive to societal expectations. It proposes a systematic framework for the enhanced ‘scripting’ of research careers by non-scientific social institutions and public expectations. It argues that such scripting must always have the flexibility to be sensitive to epistemic practices and researchers’ career stages. The advantage of a public values perspective is thus that it links the diversity of research careers with a coherent framework that reflects both professional and public expectations, as part of a renewed and reinvigorated contract between science and society.

Open science practices

Initial work on this project was conducted in the framework of the Horizon 2020 project SUPER MoRRI. SUPER MoRRI deposited all deliverables and process documents in its project repository on Open Science Framework during the lifetime of the project. These materials are being transferred to Zenodo following the project's completion. The protocol for this study is publicly available under Work Package 5.

Author contributions

Richard Woolley developed the concept presented in the paper. The authors contributed equally to the drafting and revision of the paper.

Competing interests

The authors declare they have no competing interests.

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References

Armeni, K. et al. (2021) Towards wide-scale adoption of open science practices: The role of open science communities. *Science and Public Policy* 48(5): 605-611.

Bourdieu, P. (1975) The specificity of the scientific field and the social conditions of the progress of reason. *Social Science Information* 14(6): 19-47.

Bourdieu, P. (1988) *Homo Academicus*. Stanford University Press, Stanford.

Bozeman, B. & Sarewitz, D. (2011) *Public Value Mapping and Science Policy Evaluation*, *Minerva* 49: 1-23.

EC (European Commission) (2021) *She figures 2021: gender in research and innovation: statistics and indicators*. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/06090>

EC (European Commission) (2011) *Toward a European Framework for Research Careers*. Brussels, DG RTD.

Gibbons, M, Limoges, C., Nowotny H., Schwartzman S., Scott P. & M. Trow (1994) *The new production of knowledge: the dynamics of science and research in contemporary societies*. Sage, London.

Gläser, J. (2001) Macrostructures, careers and knowledge production: A neoinstitutionalist approach. *International Journal of Technology Management* 22(7-8): 698-715.

Gläser, J. & G. Laudel (2015) *The Three Careers of an Academic*. Zentrum Technik und Gesellschaft, discussion paper Nr. 35/2015. TU Berlin.

Laudel, G., & J. Bielick (2019). How do field-specific research practices affect mobility decisions of early career researchers? *Research Policy* 48(9): article 103800.

Laudel, G., Bielick, J., & Gläser, J. (2018). Ultimately the question always is: “What do I have to do to do it right?” Scripts as explanatory factors of career decisions. *Human Relations* 72(5): 932-961.

Leonelli, S. (2023) *Philosophy of Open Science*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Merton, R. (1973) *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.

Mirowski, P. (2018) The future(s) of open science. *Social Studies of Science* 48(2): 171-203.

Owen, R., Macnaghten, P. & J. Stilgoe (2012) Responsible research and innovation: From science in society to science for society, with society. *Science and Public Policy* 39(6): 751–760.

UKRI (UK Research & Innovation) (2020) *Bullying and Harassment in Research and Innovation Environments: An evidence review*. UKRI, Swindon.

UKRI (UK Research & Innovation) (2022) *UKRI equity, diversity and inclusion strategy: draft for consultation*. UKRI, Swindon.

Vitae (2020) *Research integrity: a landscape study*. Vitae, London.

Wellcome Trust (2021) *Diversity, equity and inclusion strategy*. Wellcome Trust, London.

Whitley, R. (2000) *The Intellectual and Social Organization of the Sciences*. Oxford University Press, *Reconfiguring Knowledge Production*

Whitley, R., Gläser, J. & L. Engwall (2010) *Reconfiguring Knowledge Production: Changing Authority Relationships in the Sciences and their Consequences for Intellectual Innovation*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.